

THE TERM “CONCEPT” IN COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS THEORETICAL VIEWS ON ITS APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the article is to discuss and find out some features of lexical-semantic characteristics of using the term “concept”, “category”, and “frame” in cognitive linguistics.

Keywords: Concept, cognitive linguistic, conceptualization, categorization, paradigm, linguistic classification.

Pragmatic, sociolinguistic, cognitive and psycholinguistic principles have been rapidly developing in linguistics since the beginning of the 21st century.

One of the prominent representatives of world cognitive linguistics, the Russian scientist E.S. According to Kubryakova, "Cognitive linguistics is a relatively new, promising direction of the science of language, in the center of its analysis is language, i.e., the system of symbols that plays an important role in information realization (coding, keying) and transformation, i.e. transmission, is researched in an integral connection with their cognitive basis."

So, relying on the scientist's opinion, it can be said that: cognitive linguistics studies language phenomena in an integral connection with thought processes, at the same time, the mechanisms of language learning by humans and the processes of conceptualization and categorization are revealed, explained and creates a thorough ground for its illumination.

Cognitive linguistics is a science that studies language as a general cognitive mechanism. According to V.Z. Demyankov, the role of language structures in information processing is studied from the point of view of speech creation and perception. In this case, the subjects who create speech and perceive it - the speaker and the listener - are considered as an information processing system.

According to the scientist, "...the researcher who started in the field of linguistics eventually reaches the destination of "combined sciences". That is, a person who wants to engage in cognitive linguistics needs to be familiar with the alphabet of sciences such as psychology, neurology, epistemology, sociology, artificial intelligence, which are the basis for the emergence of this field.

Cognitive linguistics is closely related to the concept of cognitive activity. Cognitive activity is a thinking process that makes a person perceive something or reality.

The concept of cognition is also a central concept in cognitive linguistics, and it is interpreted in scientific literature as a system of processes such as perception, encoding and creation of information.

Z.D. Popova and I.A. Sternin believe that "Cognitive linguistics studies the types and forms of mental processes that occur in the process of perceiving, understanding, and, therefore, understanding reality."

According to V.A. Maslova, "Operational memory units - frames (stereotypical situations, scenarios), concepts, gestalt (integrated concepts of world lines, images) become a tool for working in cognitive linguistics. Therefore, cognitive linguistics focuses on modeling the world view and the structure of language consciousness.

Cognitive linguistics is a new stage in language learning, writes Z.I. Rezanova. "Cognitive linguistics plays an important role in the anthropocentric paradigm of linguistic classification, studying the relationship between language and the cognitive mechanism as the most ontologically important determinant".

Scientific research works in this direction were published for the first time in the USA in the mid-70s of the last century. Later, the works of European and Russian cognitive scientists began to be published gradually.

Expressing his attitude to cognitive linguistics, the Russian researcher L.V. Pravikova writes: "If cognitive linguistics is considered not from the point of view of what motivated its emergence (the study and research of thinking, perceptual activity and cognition), but from the point of view of the place of its research subject in the system of language levels, then this direction of linguistics in general is engaged in researching the meaningful parameters of the language. These are directions such as cognitive semantics, logical semantics, and frame semantics, which in turn mean the study and observation of categories and categorization, concepts and conceptualization, metaphors and metaphorization, reference and informational aspects of speech activity in cognitive language.

The scientist is more precise in his opinion about this, and distinguishes Russian cognitive linguistics from other similar directions abroad as follows: "Cognitive linguistics in the linguistics of our country (Russian).

has its own clear direction of development. If in foreign linguistics the cognitive direction appeared in connection with the study of various conventional semantics, in our country cognitive ideas, in our opinion, were revealed in connection with research in the field of nomination (naming). In this theory, the relationship between form and content in language was interpreted at the semasiological and onomasiological levels.

Thus, in cognitive linguistics, it appears as a promising science that studies the formation and development of conceptual semantics, its realization through verbal means, and its use in communication.

There are also scientists who have expressed a negative attitude to the status of cognitive linguistics, its subject, methods, goals and tasks, and the object of research. For example, the Russian linguist V. B. Kasevich, speaking about the contribution of cognitive linguistics to modern linguistics, concludes his analysis by saying: "although the approaches to language developed in this field and their results enrich linguistics, they are not a new object (or rather, subject) of research." does not create a new method, therefore it would be correct to say that there is no "cognitive linguistics", because there is no non-cognitive (psycho)linguistics itself.

E.S. Kubryakova V.B. Completely rejecting Kasevich's opinion, he puts forward his following correct idea against his opinion: "Cognitive linguistics certainly exists (because there is non-cognitive linguistics, such as structural linguistics), in the shell of which a specific understanding of the term we are interested in is formed, although it is a polysemous term. did not manage to circulate, but in any case, it is necessary to pay attention to one or another assessment given to cognitive linguistics in our country and abroad"

The place, importance of cognitive linguistics and its main differences from related linguistics can be found in the multi-volume publication "Cognitive Linguistics: Foundations, Scope and Methodology" (1999) dedicated to cognitive linguistics research. In his special book, the world's prominent cognitive linguists expressed valuable opinions on the independent status of this field in modern linguistics, most importantly, it was recognized that no matter what phenomenon of language is studied, a cognitive-functional approach to them is preferable to a formal analysis. Based on the essence of this semantic approach, the well-known typologist W. Croft also writes about it, he emphasizes the unique importance of cognitive linguistics in the typological study of language.

The scientist who gave the highest assessment to cognitive linguistics is J. Faucone, who expresses his opinion about it as follows: "The surprising success of cognitive linguistics, apparently for the first time in it, they began to connect the science of meaning formation with its development, but to the language left from ancient times Despite the fact that the approach to meaning as a tool for forming and expressing is also in cognitive linguistics, all its research methods and results are completely new.

It should be said that the processes of conceptualization and categorization are of great importance in cognitive linguistics. The main reason for this is that "Conceptualization is aimed at differentiating the minimum meaningful units of the composition (complex) of human experience - knowledge, while the process of categorization is aimed at differentiating and classifying similar units from each other and uniting them into relatively larger groups, or rather categories".

The use of this term in cognitive linguistics is primarily explained by the fact that the rapidly growing streams of language data in the form of electronic resources require the creation of automated systems for processing large text arrays to extract semantic information from texts according to predefined parameters. Frame recognition systems presented in texts greatly facilitate the process of obtaining semantic information, which means that the creation of identification (detection) algorithms and frame formation is one of the urgent tasks of modern cognitive linguistics.

Taking into account that the problems of studying the processes of conceptualization and categorization of objective reality in this study are among the most urgent and urgent issues of cognitive linguistics, description of the concept recognized by scientists as the main form of knowledge classification and the main means of conceptualizing reality; It was theoretically justified that conducting broader scientific research on terms such as category, gestalt, frame and slot, which have become a learning tool in cognitive linguistics, is the most urgent task facing modern linguists in the world.

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